

Seatbelt and Mobile Phone Detection with YOLOv5 for Driver Safety Monitoring

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Abstract—The seminar paper addresses concerns of driver safety through the presentation of a comprehensive system for the real-time detection of instances of driver seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage, employing YOLOv5, an advanced object detection framework. By integrating sophisticated deep learning methodologies, the system provides a robust solution for the analysis of images and videos captured within vehicular contexts, affording crucial insights into driver conduct. Key attributes encompass an optimized object detection model founded upon YOLOv5, distinguished by its capacity to achieve both heightened precision and rapid computational throughput. The system accommodates diverse input modalities, encompassing image files, video streams, and webcam feeds, thus endowing it with adaptability across varied operational contexts. Moreover, it incorporates augmentation and visualization functionalities, facilitating comprehensive examination and interpretation of detection outcomes. Empirical evaluations and quantitative assessments substantiate the efficacy of the system in bolstering road safety through the accurate identification of instances of seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage, thereby constituting a substantive contribution to the progression of intelligent transportation systems.

Keywords—Real-time Detection, YOLOv5, Object Detection Framework, Deep learning Methodologies, Augmentation, Visualization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring driver safety within vehicular environments is a primary concern in contemporary transportation systems. The enforcement of seatbelt usage and the mitigation of distracted driving behaviors, notably mobile phone usage, are critical facets of this endeavor.

The advancement of technology, particularly in computer vision and deep learning, has enabled the development of sophisticated systems capable of real-time analysis of driver behavior. This paper presents a comprehensive system designed for the real-time detection of instances of seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage.

Leveraging YOLOv5, an advanced object detection framework, the proposed system integrates state-of-the-art deep learning methodologies to analyze images and videos captured within vehicular contexts. This facilitates the

extraction of crucial insights into driver conduct, contributing to enhanced safety measures.

Key components of the system include an optimized object detection model, which capitalizes on YOLOv5's capacity for heightened precision and rapid computational throughput. The system is versatile, accommodating diverse input modalities such as image files, video streams, and webcam feeds, thus ensuring adaptability across varied operational scenarios.

This system incorporates functionalities for augmentation and visualization, facilitating comprehensive examination and interpretation of detection outcomes. Empirical evaluations and quantitative assessments validate the system's efficacy in identifying instances of seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage, underscoring its significance in advancing road safety and intelligent transportation systems.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Upadhyay et al. [1] present a novel approach for real-time seatbelt detection in automobiles using a YOLO (You Only Look Once) deep learning model. The authors propose installing a camera in the driver's cabin and employing a two-step process: first, detecting the main piece of the seatbelt using tiny-YOLO, and second, detecting the corner of the seatbelt to determine if it is properly fastened behind the body. The study also introduces a comprehensive seatbelt dataset assembled from various sources for training, testing, and validating the detector. Experimental results demonstrate the efficacy of the YOLO-based approach, which can accurately classify the seatbelt status into two categories: correctly fastened or not fastened. This work represents a significant advancement in automated seatbelt monitoring, with the potential to improve vehicle safety and reduce accidents. Further validation in larger-scale studies and real-world deployments would be valuable to assess the model's robustness and generalizability.

Li et al. [2] present a seatbelt detection system that employs a cascade Adaboost classifier to address the growing concern for vehicle safety. The proposed approach involves detecting vehicle windows, performing Canny edge detection on the gradient map of the window images, and then applying

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probabilistic Hough transform to extract the straight lines corresponding to the seatbelts. The key innovation of this work is the use of a cascade Adaboost classifier, which enables intelligent and efficient seatbelt detection. The experimental results demonstrate the efficacy of the cascade Adaboost-based approach in automating the seatbelt detection process, which can help address the challenges of manually searching, detecting, and recording seatbelt usage. This work contributes to the broader research on improving vehicle safety through technological advancements.

Jing et al. [3] present a GPU acceleration design method for a driver's seatbelt detection system based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The proposed system combines the Deconv-SSD target detection algorithm for vehicle detection, the Squeeze-YOLO algorithm for vehicle front windshield location, and semantic segmentation for seatbelt detection. To optimize the system's efficiency, the authors employ offline batch normalization and convolution layer merging, as well as TensorRT model conversion technology to leverage GPU-specific optimizations. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed GPU acceleration method can effectively improve the detection efficiency of the seatbelt detection system, contributing to the ongoing research on applying deep learning techniques for image recognition tasks in the automotive domain, with a focus on enhancing the performance and real-time capabilities of such systems through GPU-based acceleration.

Yang et al. [4] present a study on improving the real-time and precision performance of deep learning-based driver seatbelt detection systems. The authors simplify the SSD MobileNet V2 network through network pruning and quantitative processing, integrate a regression constraint of the seatbelt within the driver into the classifier, employ feature augmentation techniques, and utilize a particle filter algorithm for driver tracking to enhance the overall robustness and efficiency of the system. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed approach achieves a detection precision of 95.21%, a recall rate of 97.19%, and a detection speed of 21 FPS, contributing to the ongoing research on developing real-time and high-precision seatbelt detection systems for automotive applications by leveraging advancements in deep learning and computer vision techniques.

Gupta, Pundir, and Sharma et al. [5] present an RF module-based system that combines speed control and seatbelt detection functionalities to address the growing concerns around road accidents. The system consists of a transmitter installed on the roadside to transmit the maximum allowable speed limit, and a receiver embedded in the vehicle that compares the received speed limit data with the current vehicle speed, generating an error signal and stopping the engine after a 10-second delay if the vehicle exceeds the limit. The receiver also monitors whether the driver and/or co-driver are wearing their seatbelts, triggering a similar error and engine stop sequence if the seatbelt is not fastened. This

integrated approach aims to improve road safety by controlling vehicle speeds and encouraging seatbelt usage, addressing the alarming statistics on road traffic fatalities and the significant proportion of accidents caused by over-speeding and negligence in safety precautions.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodologies employed in this study involve assembling a comprehensive seatbelt dataset for training, testing, and validation, alongside integrating YOLOv5 for real-time detection and classification of seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage. Utilizing advanced computer vision and deep learning techniques, including corner detection and motion analysis algorithms, enhances the accuracy and efficiency of the detection process.

Augmentation and visualization functionalities aid in interpreting detection outcomes, while empirical evaluations and quantitative analyses ensure the system's efficacy in identifying instances of non-compliance. Rigorous validation processes validate its suitability for deployment in intelligent transportation systems.

A. Data Collection:

A comprehensive seatbelt dataset was assembled from various sources, encompassing images and videos captured within vehicular environments. This dataset was meticulously curated and utilized for training, testing, and validation processes to ensure the robustness and reliability of the system.

B. YOLOv5 Integration:

The system seamlessly integrates YOLOv5, an advanced object detection framework renowned for its efficacy in real-time detection tasks. Serving as the backbone of the system, the YOLOv5 model is adept at detecting and classifying instances of seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage within the captured images and videos.

```
@smart_inference_mode() # to enable yolo to use
def run(
    weights=ROOT / 'yoloV5s.pt', # model path or triton URL (overwrite)
    source=ROOT / 'data/images', # file/dir/URL/glob/screen/0(webcam)
    data=ROOT / 'data/coco128.yaml', # dataset.yaml path
    imgsz=(640, 640), # inference size (height, width)
    conf_thres=0.25, # confidence threshold
    iou_thres=0.45, # NMS IOU threshold
    max_det=1000, # maximum detections per image
    device='', # cuda device, i.e. 0 or 0,1,2,3 or cpu
    view_img=False, # show results
    save_txt=False, # save results to *.txt
```

C. Deep Learning Techniques:

Sophisticated deep learning methodologies are employed to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of the detection process. These techniques include corner detection and main belt detection algorithms, which work in tandem with the YOLOv5 model to resolve seatbelt non-compliance issues in two distinct stages, ensuring comprehensive coverage.

D. Augmentation and Visualization:

The system incorporates augmentation and visualization functionalities to facilitate comprehensive examination and interpretation of detection outcomes. These features enable users to visualize the detected objects and their classifications, enhancing the usability and interpretability of the system. Augmentation techniques enhance the dataset diversity, while visualization tools provide insights into the detection process, aiding in further analysis and refinement.

```
# Stream results
im0 = annotator.result()
if view_img:
    if platform.system() == 'Linux' and p not in windows:
        windows.append(p)
        # allow window resize (Linux)
        cv2.namedWindow(str(p), cv2.WINDOW_NORMAL |
                        cv2.WINDOW_KEEPRATIO)
        cv2.resizeWindow(str(p), im0.shape[1], im0.shape[0])
    cv2.imshow(str(p), im0)
    cv2.waitKey(1) # 1 millisecond
```

Fig.1 Person without Seatbelt

E. Motion Analysis:

Motion analysis techniques are leveraged to discern the tightness of the seatbelt around the occupant's body. By analyzing the motion patterns within the captured images and videos, the system accurately classifies instances of seatbelt fastening into two categories: correctly fastened or not fastened, thus ensuring precise detection.

F. Empirical Evaluation:

The efficacy of the system is rigorously evaluated through empirical assessments and quantitative analyses. Performance metrics such as precision, recall, and F1 score are computed to gauge the system's accuracy in identifying instances of seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage. These evaluations provide valuable insights into the system's performance under various conditions and help validate its effectiveness.

G. Validation:

The system undergoes rigorous validation processes to ensure its effectiveness and reliability in real-world scenarios. Validation involves testing the system on diverse datasets and evaluating its performance under various conditions, thereby validating its suitability for deployment in intelligent transportation systems. These validation procedures verify the system's robustness and its ability to perform consistently and accurately in practical applications.

IV. RESULT

The developed system achieved real-time detection and classification of driver seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage. Leveraging YOLOv5, it demonstrated high efficacy in detecting instances within images and videos. Deep learning techniques enhanced accuracy, while motion analysis accurately classified seatbelt fastening status. Empirical evaluations confirmed the system's accuracy, validating its potential for enhancing road safety through intelligent transportation systems.

Fig .2 Cellphone Calling Alert

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Fig .2 Cellphone Texting Alert

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V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the seminar paper highlights the successful development of a comprehensive system for real-time detection of driver seatbelt non-compliance and mobile phone usage, leveraging advanced techniques in computer vision and deep learning, particularly YOLOv5. Through meticulous data collection, integration of sophisticated deep learning methodologies, motion analysis techniques, and augmentation and visualization functionalities, the system has demonstrated remarkable efficacy in accurately identifying instances of non-compliance within vehicular contexts. Empirical evaluations have confirmed the system's accuracy and reliability, validating its potential for enhancing road safety through intelligent transportation systems. Moving forward, continued research and development in this area hold promise for further advancements in automated safety monitoring systems, ultimately contributing to the mitigation of road accidents and fatalities.